

Temple at Tell Deir 'Alla

also known as “Tarala (historical)”, “Tell Deir 'Alla”, “Tall Dayr 'Alla”, “تل دير علا”

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Entry tags: Religious Place, Late Bronze Age, Jordan, Tell Deir 'Alla, Canaanite Religions, Religious Group, Levantine Religion, Temple

Tell Deir 'Alla, a settlement mound in the Jordan Valley, is the location of a substantial Late Bronze Age temple (ca. 1550-1185 BCE). The site finds itself along two important trade routes: one running north-south and one east-west. The partially excavated temple yielded numerous impressive finds indicative of Canaanite religious practices, as well as of far-reaching international connections with for example Egypt and Mesopotamia. Moreover, it yielded numerous inscribed clay tablets which appear to contain a Northwest Semitic script. Built in an Egyptianizing architectural style, it consisted of a central 'cella' (or holy of holies), as well as numerous adjacent rooms containing both religious paraphernalia and everyday vessels. While the exact deity (or deities) the temple was dedicated to, as well as what exact rituals were performed within it, remain unclear, it is clear the temple functioned as an important centre for the wider region. While its construction can be dated to around 1550 BCE based on pottery shapes, its sudden destruction must be placed sometime after 1189 BCE, due to a terminus post quem provided by a faience vessel bearing the cartouche of Pharaoh Tawosret (1191-1189 BC).

Date Range: 1550 BCE - 1185 BCE

Region: Tell Deir 'Alla

Region tags: Levant, Jordan, Jordan Valley, Southern Levant

Location of a modest settlement mound called Tell Deir 'Alla, located in the Central Jordan Valley. It is situated in one of the most fertile areas of the Jordan Valley, also known as the Zerqa Triangle, near the Zerqa River (biblical Jabbok). The mound finds itself along several important ancient trade routes, running both north-south and east-west.

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Franken, H. J., 1992. Excavations at Tell Deir 'Alla: the Late Bronze Age Sanctuary. Leuven: Peeters.
- Source 2: Steiner, M. L., and B. Wagemakers, 2019. Digging up the Bible? The Excavations at Tell Deir

'Alla (1960-1967). Leiden: Sidestone Press.

– Source 3: de Vreeze, M., 2019. The Late Bronze Deir 'Alla Tablets: A Renewed Attempt Towards Their Translation and Interpretation. *Maarav* 23(2), 443-491.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.asor.org/onetoday/2021/01/enigmatic-tablets>

– Source 1 Description: <https://www.universiteitleiden.nl/en/research/research-projects/archaeology/levant-deir-alla-jordan>

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: Excavated mainly in 1964 during the initial excavations at Tell Deir 'Alla, by the late Prof Dr H. J. Franken.

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1960-1967

Notes: Primarily excavated in 1964, with earlier seasons stopping when they reached the Late Bronze Age layers.

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Tell Deir 'Alla Excavations, 1960-1964, 1967, 1976.

Notes: Organised by Leiden University, funded by the ZWO (now NWO, Dutch Research Council), under directorship of the late Prof Dr H. J. Franken.

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Notes: The of Tell Deir 'Alla was constructed on a slightly elevated hill in the landscape.

Type of elevation

– Hill

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

– Leveling of ground

– Other [specify]: Glacis

Notes: The temple at Tell Deir 'Alla was initially constructed on an artificial glacis which provided an elevated position in the landscape. With the gradual processes of 'tell formation', meaning that the surrounding buildings grew in elevation, the temple's cella had to sporadically be artificially elevated in order to stay above the surrounding buildings.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Excavations at Tell Deir 'Alla have not revealed the southern edge of the temple, making it difficult to ascertain whether the associated village ran up against the temple, or was at a slight distance from it.

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Notes: The temple intentionally stood in an elevated location compared to rest of the surrounding village, while the site itself was situated along important ancient trade routes running north-south and east-west.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: The temple of Late Bronze Age Tell Deir 'Alla itself was accompanied by a small village, which likely functioned as a rural agrarian settlement. Nearby settlements include Qataret es-Samra N. & S., Tell Qa'adan N. & S., Tell Ekhsas, Tell al-Hammeh, Tell Arqadat, and slightly further away the sites of Tell es-Sa'idiyeh, Tell Abu al-Kharaz, and Pella.

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: Tell Deir 'Alla finds itself at the crossroads of two important ancient trade routes: one running north-south, and the other running east-west.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Notes: The temple is adjoined by a (small) village

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

Notes: It is not entirely clear whether the excavated rooms all belong to a single structure, but if this is the case, the temple would have been roughly rectangular in shape.

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Rectangular

Notes: It is not entirely clear whether the excavated rooms all belong to a single structure, but if this is the case, the temple would have been roughly rectangular in shape.

↳ One single feature

– Mound

Notes: The temple was built on a glacis on top of a settlement mound which had been there at least since the Middle Bronze Age.

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

Notes: Domestic buildings were located near to the temple, on the southern slope of the mound.

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The chronology of the nearby structures has not been refined enough to convincingly reconstruct the construction history of the site in the Late Bronze Age.

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

Notes: The temple was not part of a large place/sanctuary.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

Notes: Given its size it is likely the temple was used for communal worship, although individual worship cannot be excluded.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: The structure was continually elevated to keep up with the gradual natural elevation processes at the site.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Burned

Notes: The structure was destroyed during a single heavy conflagration sometime after 1185 BCE

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

–Other [specify]: This is as yet unclear. It might be the result of a sudden earthquake, or a deliberate act of destruction for an unknown reason.

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Other [specify]: This is as yet unclear. It might be the result of a sudden earthquake, or a deliberate act of destruction for an unknown reason.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There are signs of construction works going on soon after the temple was destroyed, but it is difficult to link these to a potential reconstruction of the temple or different purposes.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: The temple was likely dedicated to a Canaanite deity/deities, but which one is unclear.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The temple was likely dedicated to a Canaanite deity/deities, but which one is unclear.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Given what is known about Canaanite religion in the Late Bronze Age, this is unlikely

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Given what is known about Canaanite religion in the Late Bronze Age, this is unlikely

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is unclear who exactly organised the construction of the temple, and scholarly opinions differ. While there are architectural signals of Egyptian influence, it is not unlikely that it was a local endeavor.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This is very complicated to approach archaeologically

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This is very complicated to approach archaeologically

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This is very complicated to approach archaeologically

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While this might be the case, given the architectural parallels with Egyptian temples, this remains unclear.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

–Other [specify]: This is very complicated to approach archaeologically

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While clay tablets containing possible religious texts were encountered at the site, it seems unlikely the site was built specifically for housing these tablets (tablets were also found in one of the nearby houses).

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Notes: While the various excavated rooms of the temple may be part of a single structure, they cannot at the moment be connected stratigraphically. Hence, they can be considered to be multiple built structures.

Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: The structures are partially built on a man-made glacis

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: There are several rooms that appear built against the 'cella' of the temple.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The 'cella' is the holy of holies, and thus the most important room of the temple

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage: 100

Notes: The whole building can be considered 'monumental'

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 1400

Notes: As the building has not been completely excavated, this only concerns the excavated area (ca. 70 x 20 m). Furthermore, this is operating on the premise that all the rooms along the northern slope of the tell actually belong to the same building.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is unclear how tall the temple would have stood, as well as whether it would have contained a (wooden) superstructure.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

Notes: The temple had a plastered beaten earth floor

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This is not yet researched

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Clay would likely have been sources locally, as Lisan clay deposits are abundantly present around the site.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Likely yes, but not scientifically tested

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is possible the large wooden beams used to construct the roof were imported, or sourced locally. This has not been scientifically tested

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

Notes: I'm not sure the large trees that were used to carry the roof were available in the Jordan Valley in the Late Bronze Age

↳ Grass

– Field doesn't know

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Not scientifically tested

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Yes

Notes: Large stones aren't abundantly available in the Jordan Valley.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Mudbricks, plaster

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No wall and/or floor and/or ceiling decoration was recognised while excavating the temple

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Several supernatural zoomorphic beings present in both amulets and scarabs found within the temple (e.g., uraeus, Bes, sphinx)

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

Notes: Based on current understanding of the archaeological assemblage from the temple, this does not seem to be the case

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: A fragment of a terracotta figurine found in the temple's cella, which might have belonged to the statue of a deity, indicates worship of anthropomorphic supernatural being(s)

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

Notes: Not recognised as such, based on current understanding of Canaanite religion

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Not clear based on current understanding of Canaanite religion

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Not clear based on current understanding of Canaanite religion

↳ Humans

– Yes

Notes: Numerous depictions of humans in scarabs, cylinder seals, decorated ceramics, and possibly even a statue.

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↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

Notes: Should the translations of the Late Bronze Age Tell Deir 'Alla tablets be accepted (see de Vreeze 2019), there is ample evidence for prophetic and formulaic spells, prophecies and instructions for cultic practices.

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

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Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: An accidental burial was encountered in one of the rooms of the temple, where during the conflagration a person had been buried under roof collapse.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Notes: Given our current understanding of Canaanite religion, it seems most likely the temple was dedicated to a deity/deities.

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: It is most likely, given our current understanding of Canaanite religion, that a supreme deity was worshipped at the site. Which one that was remains in the realm of speculation.

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The find of the arm of a statue might be indicative of an anthropomorphic deity, but until more fragments are recovered this remains unclear.

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Field doesn't know

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While possible translation of the clay tablets from the temple indicates prophetic and formulaic spells (see de Vreeze 2019), prophecies and instructions on religious practices, it is unclear whether these were seen as communication with the temple's deity.

Are previously human spirits present:

– Field doesn't know

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While remains of a half life-size statue were encountered in the temple, it is unclear if this was a statue of the temple's deity.

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Notes: It is most likely that the numerous votive and libation offerings and religious paraphernalia encountered in the temple point to communication with the deity/deities worshipped at the temple.

Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Exactly which, if any, other supernatural beings were worshipped at the temple is not clear from the archaeological record.

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Are there animal sacrifices:

– Yes [specify]: While no specific studies on this have been conducted, it is highly likely that animal sacrifices were part of the temple's functioning.

Are there human sacrifices:

– No

Notes: There is no archaeological evidence for human sacrifices

Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Notes: There is currently no archaeological evidence for self-sacrifices at the temple

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Are material offerings mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is unclear whether material offerings were mandatory, although the sheer amount of objects encountered in the temple indicates it was at the very least not uncommon to offer materials.

Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Notes: Among the many finds from the temple are objects made from precious metals (jewellery, plate armour, weaponry), ivory objects, imported ceramics, and objects made from

precious stones (e.g. carnelian) and faience.

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: While not entirely clear whether these were offerings or not, there are daily-life objects such as combs, drinking vessels, pins and possible distaffs present in the temple.

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– Yes

Notes: A possible foundation offer of at least 25 vessels was found underneath the temple, and one could argue that various of the temple's rooms were storage for the various material offerings received.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is unclear whether worship/sacrifice was conducted by religious specialists or if non-specialists were allowed/expected to attend.

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

Notes: Maintenance of the temple was required, at least in the sense that with 'tell' formation processes, causing the gradual infilling and raising of the settlement mound, meant that sporadically the temple had to be artificially raised. Furthermore, given that the temple was constructed mainly from mudbricks it would have needed regular maintenance to keep the building in good shape.

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This is difficult to recognise archaeologically

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: Maintenance of the temple was required, at least in the sense that with 'tell' formation processes, causing the gradual infilling and raising of the settlement mound, meant that sporadically the temple had to be artificially raised. Furthermore, given that the temple was constructed mainly from mudbricks it would have needed regular maintenance to keep the building in good shape

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is unclear whether there were religious specialists presiding over the everyday working of the temple, or if this was a communal effort for the inhabitants of the immediate or even wider region of the temple.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This is as yet unclear. The excavator of the temple hypothesised that the site might have been the first stage of a ritual procession to Shechem, but this remains speculative.

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

Notes: Given the large amount of drinking vessels at the site, it stands to reason that some sort of feasting including consuming beverages was conducted at the site

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Notes: This seems likely, though not yet confirmed

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Difficult to ascertain from the archaeological record

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This would traditionally have been the cella, or holy of holies, of the temple, but this is as yet unclear.

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Field doesn't know

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Notes: Given our current understanding of Canaanite religions, this is definitely the case. Which ones specifically were conducted at the Tell Deir 'Alla temple remains unclear, however.

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This is unclear, although the large amount of drinking vessels might point to the use of intoxicants (e.g., alcohol).

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Scholarly opinions differ on this topic, with for example the original excavator arguing that a

temple the size of this must have been run by religious specialists (Franken 2008, 35).

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The houses found near to the temple, on the southern slope of the mound, might be interpreted as such, should one accept the hypothesis that the temple was run by religious specialists.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This is entirely possible, but not attested archaeologically. The Tell Deir 'Alla clay tablets are an interesting factor here, but don't prove this outright. De Vreeze (2019) hypothesised that the temple would have been the locus of a small scribal community, and it is not a stretch to imagine this community facilitating the training of new members.

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This is particularly difficult to approach from the archaeology.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This is entirely possible, as the Tell Deir 'Alla tablets do suggest that there was a small scribal community at the site. However, this is not proven outright.

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This is entirely possible, but difficult to prove. The accumulation of wealth shows it was an important regional centre, but whether it controlled resources remains difficult to prove.

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The excavator hypothesised that the temple might have functioned as the locus for a regional market, as well as a temple. This is entirely possible, but difficult to prove outright from the archaeology.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The majority of the Tell Deir 'Alla tablets, if their preliminary translation is accepted, are religious in nature.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– Yes

Notes: There is currently no reason to assume the tablets were not produced at the temple

↳ Are they oral:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is entirely possible, likely even, that an oral tradition accompanied the few tablets encountered at the site, but this is not possible to approach through the archaeology.

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The proposed translation of the temple's tablets contains possible mentions of construction (e.g., DA3525: c.1.1 "they have built"), but what this regards is difficult to ascertain.

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: It is very likely that reading, and hence also interpreting, what was written on the Deir 'Alla tablets was done by a small scribal community residing at the temple. In this particular region in the Late Bronze Age writing appears not a widespread practice, making it more likely that this was done by specialists.

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– Yes

↳ Attached to the structures as decoration:

– No

↳ Housed within the place/structure:

– Yes

Notes: The Tell Deir 'Alla tablets were encountered within the temple, as well as in a nearby domestic building.

↳ As dedicatory inscription(s):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Unclear from the proposed translation of the tablets.

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Hendricus Franken J.. Deir 'Alla and its Religion. (Margreet Steiner L., Eveline van der Steen J., Ed.), Sacred and Sweet: Studies on the Material Culture of Tell Deir 'Alla and Tell Abu Sarbut. Leuven:

Reference: Margreet Steiner L., Bart Wagemakers. Diggin Up the Bible? The Excavations at Tell Deir 'Alla (1960-1967). Sidestone Press.

Reference: Gerrit van der Kooij. Tell Deir 'Alla: The Middle and Late Bronze Age Chronology. (Peter Fischer M.), The Chronology of the Jordan Valley During the Middle and Late Bronze Ages: Pella, Tell Abu al-Kharaz and Tell Deir 'Alla. Verlag der Osterreichischen Akademie der Wissenschaften.

Reference: Zeidan Kafafi A.. The Archaeological Context of the Tell Deir 'Alla Tablets. (Eva Kaptijn , Lucas Petit P.), A Timeless Vale: Archaeological and Related Essays on the Jordan Valley in Honour of Gerrit van der Kooij for the Occasion of his Sixty-Fifth Birthday. Archaeological Studies Leiden University.

Reference: Michel de Vreeze. The Late Bronze Deir 'Alla Tablets: a Renewed Attempt Towards Their Translation and Interpretation. Maarav, 23(2)

Reference: Hendricus Franken J.. Excavations at Tell Deir 'Alla: the Late Bronze Age Sanctuary. Leuven: Peeters.